

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF MARKETING TOOLS IN INCREASING THE INTERNATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF THE TEXTILE ENTERPRISE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520620>

Abstract. *In this article, the level of competitiveness of the market, the solvency of the population, the quality of transport and logistics services, their cost, the efficiency of enterprise management, the use of marketing, innovative activities, and the reduction of service costs compared to competitors are considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, competition, service, production, cost, innovation, integration, export.*

INTRODUCTION

The socially oriented model of Uzbekistan's own market economy is related to the development of foreign economic activity, as well as the determination of the ways of integration into world economic relations, and the perspective of the market economy is related to its international integration.

After the independence of our country, the implementation of structural changes in the economy, the establishment of export-oriented production enterprises and the production of competitive products through technical and technological updating, the acquisition of new territories, and the measures aimed at further increasing the country's export potential were given great importance.

One of the tasks set by the President included the following: In order to further stimulate export, it is necessary to harmonize the technical regulatory system with international standards. One of our main goals is to export quality and certified products to the foreign market under the name of "Uzbek brand". The light industry of Uzbekistan is one of the multi-faceted, innovative and attractive sectors of the country's economy. Today, the share of light industry in the GDP is 3.8%, 26.2% in the volume of industrial products, 44% in relation to non-food products, also shows that the sector has a great role in the economy of our republic. The average annual increase in the volume of product production in industrial enterprises is 20%, and the increase in the volume of export is 10%.

Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical application. Among them, we include famous scientists such as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall possible

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing, while the research carried out in the field of marketing in our country for many years was based on national characteristics. R. Ibragimov to them. Yo. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musaeva and others can be included.

Research methodolog

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Competition is a serious struggle of people, especially in economic, as well as in other spheres of social life. From the point of view of economy, competition is the struggle of sellers (producers) to meet the demands of consumers, as well as the struggle of buyers to buy the most useful goods for themselves under the most favorable conditions. On the one hand, competition prevents economic stagnation and is a guarantee of social development, on the other hand, loss of stability, conflicts, bankruptcy, and dismissal of employees are integral parts of competition.

Analysis and results

M. Porter justified the fact that the competitive advantage of the enterprise in the domestic and foreign markets is highly dependent on the conditions formed in the country where the enterprise is located, that is, the availability of labor, the abundance of natural resources, the state's protectionist policy towards local enterprises, differences in the management practices of enterprises and other factors.

In today's advanced market conditions, a method of competition that is not related to price is to distinguish one's own goods from similar goods of competitors, to give it unique characteristics for the buyer, to increase the level of technical service, to develop advanced forms of selling goods, to improve the functional aspects and structure of the company's activities, to meet customer requests. such as taking into account the uniqueness is preferred. For this, competitors use the release of new goods, their improvement, quality improvement, various additional services and offering after-sales service guarantees. In non-price competition, relative financial stability is ensured and this allows for effective management of the enterprise. The non-price method of competition is more effective, because competitors cannot respond as quickly as in price competition. That is why non-price competition is also called effective competition. Although the method of non-price competition requires more effort and financial expenditure than price competition, these costs are fully justified in cases of success. Depending on the company's goals and capabilities, one of the following options for competitive behavior can be chosen: Although the method of non-price competition requires more effort and financial expenditure than price competition, these costs are fully justified in cases of success. Depending on the company's goals and capabilities, one of the following options for competitive behavior can be chosen: Although the method of non-price competition requires more effort and financial expenditure than price competition, these costs are fully justified in cases of success. Depending on the company's goals and capabilities, one of the following options for competitive behavior can be chosen:

creation of new products, technology, sales methods, service and advertising;

"copying" from innovators in the short term with low costs;

to maintain the achievements as long as possible by improving the quality and expanding the assortment.

Companies engaged in business are often called "first movers".

Factors affecting the effectiveness of the enterprise's marketing policy can be divided into two main groups: external and internal factors.

The level of competitiveness of the market, the solvency of the population, legal-regulatory, natural-climate and geographical conditions belong to the external factors, and the quality of transport and logistics services, their cost, the efficiency of enterprise management, the

use of marketing, innovative activities, the financial situation of enterprises, etc. belong to the internal factors. enters.

One of the components of the marketing policy is the ability to correctly define the pricing policy, which strengthens the competitive advantage:

- a) achieving resource savings, that is, reducing the cost of providing services compared to competitors;
- b) increase the volume of transport and logistics services;
- c) to reduce the cost of service and increase the volume at the same time.

In all three cases, the price emerges as a derivative factor with a positive effect.

When developing the product policy, the following information is taken into account: the level of freshness of the product; assortment of the produced product; the number of similar goods or imitation goods in this market segment; its level of compliance with the needs of specific buyers of this market segment; product quality; technological complexity; the level of requirements for pre-sale and after-sale service; the appropriateness of standardization or commodity flexibility; for new goods; patent protection and patent purity; that the existing organizational structure of the company is compatible with the new development; the size of the costs of creating a new product; Compulsory product certification in the target market; profitability of production and sale of new goods in the target market; investment payback period; the period of development of the new assortment and its optimization;

Modernization and diversification of the leading branches of industry, introduction of modern technologies of processing of raw materials and semi-finished products, targeted support of productions highly competitive in the world market, helped to increase the share of processing industry in production.

If in 2015, the share of the processing industry in the total volume of industrial production was 73.8%, by 2021 it will increase to 80.3%.

In the total volume of industrial production, the volume of production of products with high added value increased in the following sectors: food, textiles, chemicals, pharmaceuticals and other sectors.

Only in 2021, compared to the previous year, the increase in the volume of production in the processing industry - 6.4%, including the production of basic pharmaceutical products and preparations - 40.3%, chemical products, rubber and plastic goods - 34.4%, other non-metallic mineral products - 20.9%, food products, beverages, tobacco products - 10.8%, textile products, clothing, leather products - 9, was 0%.

Table 1

Production of industrial products by types of economic activity(in percent)

	2015 year	2021 year	Growth rate 2021 compared to 2015, in percent
Total	100.0	100.0	156.1
including:			
mining and open pit operations	15.0	9.6	121.0
processing industry	73.8	80.3	166.6

of which:			
textile products, production of clothes and leather products	14.4	16.7	168.8
electricity, gas, steam supply and air conditioning	10.7	9.4	125.2
water supply, sewage system, waste collection and disposal	0.5	0.7	165.9

As can be seen from the table above. light industry, including the textile industry, is gaining an important place in the industrial sectors of our country. At the same time, the importance of textile products in the export structure of our country is increasing. in 2021In the structure of Uzbekistan's exports, the group of other goods has a certain place with a share of 35.7%, and the volume of textile products included in this group is 1133.2 mln. was USD and increased by 22.8% compared to the same period last year.

Modernization and diversification of the textile and sewing-knitting industry is the most important condition for expanding the volume and types of ready-made competitive products that are in high demand in foreign markets, increasing the efficiency and profitability of growing and processing raw cotton.

Today, a textile network with high production potential has been formed in the republic, where about 7,000 enterprises are operating. Cotton fiber production capacity of 1.4 million tons has been created, of which about 60 percent is used to meet the needs of local textile enterprises.

First of all, the existence of systemic problems related to the establishment of the production of finished products, the organization of network management, the distribution of resources and production capacities, and the lack of high qualification of personnel lead to the low profitability of the cultivation of raw cotton and its processing, the production and export of finished products. due to the fact that it is not at the levelis coming

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for the Rapid Development of the Textile and Sewing-Knitting Industry" defines the first complex of measures to solve existing problems, as well as to expand the production of high-quality textile products and promote them to world markets. gave

With this document, the following important directions of further reform of the textile industry were defined, in particular:

- increasing the share of the textile industry in the economy, increasing the volume and quality of textile products produced in the country;
- a fundamental revision of the management system of the textile industry;
- further improvement of the standardization and certification system in the field of textile industry;
- wide introduction of advanced information and communication technologies to the network;
- implementation of the cluster model of textile industry development;
- ensuring the balance of the distribution of raw material resources and the location of the network enterprises being established in the interrelationship with the development of logistics and engineering infrastructure;

- wide implementation of advanced innovation technologies, know-how, design developments in the production process, localization of production of modern samples of fittings and accessories;
- radical improvement of the system of personnel training, retraining and advanced training for the textile industry.

JSC "Uzbekengilsanoat" is actively attracting investments, ensuring stable growth of production and export volumes. The share of semi-finished textile products in the total volume of export was equal to 14.4%. In 2021, the export volume was 1090 million dollars. In 2015-2021, the volume of export of light industrial products is 660 mln. 1090 million dollars. dollar, or in other words, the export volume increased by 1.6 times.

If we analyze the export structure of the product, we can see that the share of cotton kalava yarn in the total export of light industrial products is decreasing, and the share of yarn yarn and ready-made knitted and crocheted goods is increasing (Table 2).

Table 2

Export structure of JSC "Uzbekengilsanoat" in 2020-2021

Export of light industrial products, %	Cotton thread	Ready-made knitwear	Threading	Silk products	Other products
2020 year	44.2	16.8	4.4	1.0	10.6
2021 year	35.4	18.7	6.9	3.1	15.9

As can be seen from this picture, today cotton kalava yarn occupies a large part of the export. However, according to the order of the President, the share of ready-made knitted garments should be increased sharply in the coming years.

Until today, local textile enterprises had to buy cotton fiber from the monopoly supplier at export prices - "Uzpakhtasanoatexport" JSC. This procedure reduced the profitability and competitiveness of textile production.

According to the experiment initiated by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, enterprises of the textile industry will finance the main expenses of farms for the cultivation of cotton raw material by giving an advance of at least 60% of the contracted value. In this case, the cotton raw materials supplied to the enterprises are used only for further deep processing and production of ready competitive products.

Today, a textile industry with a huge production potential has been formed in the republic, and nearly 7,000 enterprises are effectively operating in its system. Also, capacities for the production of 1.4 million tons of cotton fiber have been created, and about 60 percent of this raw material is used to meet the needs of textile enterprises of our country. If only 436 organizations were part of JSC "Uzbekengilsanoat" before, now all enterprises and organizations of the textile industry can become members of "Uztoqiliksanoat" Association.

This provides a number of advantages for local manufacturers. In particular, enterprises that are members of the "Uztogamichiliksanoat" Association are exempted from paying customs fees for imported cotton, artificial and synthetic fibers, wool, raw materials and other materials necessary for the production of textile products that are not produced in the republic (except for fees for processing documents at the customs office). In addition, the Association "Uztogamiliksanoat" has been given the right to file a claim in the interests of its members, to file

complaints about the decisions of state bodies and other organizations, actions (inaction) of officials during the court process without paying the state duty.

In particular, this year, 34 investment projects aimed at modernization of existing enterprises, technical and technological re-equipment and creation of new capacities were implemented. The total cost of these projects is 356.9 million. is equal to 151.7 million dollars, export potential. made up the dollar.

At the same time, the export indicators of the industry were also discussed at the press conference. 1.16 billion in 2021. it was noted that the dollar product is expected to be exported. Products produced in our country are delivered to more than 50 countries of the world. The share of products with high added value was more than 40 percent. If at the beginning of 2021 there were 293 exporting enterprises in our country, by the end of the year their total number reached 350. Meanwhile, the efforts of 64 trading houses operating in different countries of the world serve to further increase the export performance of the industry.

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